

MADANIY XABARDORLIKNI OSHIRISH VA EKOLOGIK BARQAROR TURIZMNI RIVOJLANTIRISH | xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman

YASHIL IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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«Og‘ir ekologik sharoitga qaramasdan, mamlakatimiz taraqqiyotiga munosib hissa qo‘shib kelayotgan Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasini, uning barcha shahar, tuman va ovullarini kompleks tarzda rivojlantirish, mehnatkash va matonatli, oqko‘ngil va bag‘rikeng qoraqalpoq elining hayotini obod va farovon etishga har qachongidan ham ustuvor ahamiyat qaratamiz.

Bizning oliy va ezgu maqsadimiz – birgalikdagi fidokorona mehnatimiz bilan Yangi O‘zbekiston tarkibida Yangi Qoraqalpog‘istonni bunyod etishdir.»

Sh.M.MIRZIYOYEV
O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti

Prezident: “Bu ko‘prik o‘zbek va qoraqalpoq xalqlari o‘rtasidagi og‘zibirlik va hamkorlik ko‘prigidir”.

Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasini Xorazm viloyati bilan bog‘lovchi ko‘prik. Asosiy qo‘shma ko‘prikning uzunligi 413 metr bo‘lib, eni 8 metr; har bir oraliq‘i 66 metrni tashkil qiladi. Uning 7 ta ustuni 6 ta oraliqqa o‘rnatilgan.

KIRISH

2024-yilning 17–18-may kunlari Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasi Xo‘jayli tumanida o‘tkazilgan «Madaniy xabardorlikni oshirish va ekologik barqaror turizmni rivojlantirish» mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman Qoraqalpog‘istonning boy madaniy, etnografik va ekologik merosini keng jamoatchilikka tanitishda hamda turizm infratuzilmalarini mustahkamlashda muhim qadam bo‘ldi

Anjumanning asosiy maqsadi Qoraqalpog‘istonda turizm salohiyatini jahon turizm bozoriga olib kirish va madaniy xabardorlikni oshirishdir. Qoraqalpog‘iston o‘zining tarixiy boyliklari, arxeologik yodgorliklari va o‘ziga xos tabiiy manzaralari bilan dunyo sayyohlarini jalb etadigan katta jozibadorlikka ega. Bu hududda jahon madaniy va tabiiy merosi obyektlariga mansub ko‘plab joylar mavjud bo‘lib, ularning aksariyati turizm infratuzilmasini rivojlantirishga asos bo‘ladi.

Xususan, Qoraqalpog‘istondagi insoniyat tamaddunidan hikoya qiluvchi arxeologik yodgorliklar bisyor. Hozirgi kunda Qoraqalpog‘istonda 300 dan ortiq arxeologik obyektlar mavjud bo‘lib, ulardan eng mashhurlari – Ko‘hna Urganch, Tupraqal‘a, Ellikqal‘a va Ayoqal‘a hududlaridagi qadimiy manzillardir. Bular, o‘z navbatida, sayyohlar uchun jozibadorlikni oshirib, hududning turistik imkoniyatlarini kengaytiradi.

Anjumanda uchta asosiy yo‘nalish bo‘yicha muhokamalar o‘tkazildi. Birinchi yo‘nalish Qoraqalpog‘istonda turizmni rivojlantirish tendensiyalariga bag‘ishlanib, mahalliy infratuzilmalarni takomillashtirish hamda turizm xizmatlarini kengaytirish bo‘yicha takliflar ishlab chiqildi. Ikkinchi yo‘nalishda etnografik turizmni rivojlantirish, xususan, mahalliy hunarmandchilikni targ‘ib etish va milliy madaniy boyliklarni namoyish qilish masalalari muhokama qilindi. Uchinchi yo‘nalish Qoraqalpog‘istonning ekologik turizm salohiyatini jahon turizm bozorida zamonaviy marketing strategiyalari orqali targ‘ib qilish masalalariga bag‘ishlandi.

Ushbu anjuman va uning natijalari Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasida turizmni rivojlantirish yo‘lida muhim qadamdir. Turizm, madaniy meros va ekologik yo‘nalishlar bo‘yicha ishlab chiqilgan taklif va tavsiyalar hududni xalqaro turistik xaritada o‘z o‘rniga ega bo‘lishiga yordam beradi.

Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasi tarixiy, madaniy va tabiiy boyliklarga ega hudud sifatida nafaqat O‘zbekiston, balki butun Markaziy Osiyoda alohida o‘rin tutadi. Bu hududni «ochiq osmon ostidagi arxeologik muzey» deb atash mumkin, chunki bu yerda qadimiy Xorazm madaniyatining markazi bo‘lgan Qoraqalpog‘istonda nafaqat arxeologik meros, balki etnografik va ekologik turizmni rivojlantirish uchun katta imkoniyatlar mavjud.

Qoraqalpog‘istonda o‘tkaziladigan «Madaniy xabardorlikni oshirish va ekologik barqaror turizmni rivojlantirish» mavzusidagi xalqaro anjuman ana

shunday salohiyatni namoyon etish va rivojlantirish maqsadida tashkil etilgan. Anjuman doirasida turli olimlar, tadqiqotchilar va xalqaro ekspertlar ishtirokida ekologik barqarorlik va madaniy merosni saqlash masalalari muhokama qilinib, zamonaviy turizm yo‘nalishlaridagi ilmiy-nazariy takliflar ishlab chiqildi.

Anjumanda uchta asosiy yo‘nalish bo‘yicha quyidagi muhokamalar o‘tkazildi:

- *Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasida turizmni rivojlantirish tendensiyalari;*
- *Etnografik turizmni tashkil etishning asosiy xususiyatlari;*
- *Qoraqalpog‘istonning ekologik turizm salohiyatini jahon turizm bozorida targ‘ib qilishning zamonaviy marketing strategiyalari.*

Anjuman va uning natijalari Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasida ekologik va etnografik turizm nafaqat hududning iqtisodiy rivojlanishiga, balki madaniy merosini saqlash va dunyoga tanitishga yordam berishi olgari surildi.

Anjumanda xalqaro institutlar vakillarining qatnashishi bejiz emas. Qoraqalpog‘istonning boy tarixi va Xorazm madaniyati bilan bog‘liq bo‘lgan qadimiy yodgorliklar va arxeologik topinmalar bu hududni nafaqat tarixchilar, arxeologlar uchun, balki turistlar uchun ham jozibadorligini oshirib boradi.

Masalan, Ko‘kcha III qabristoni – qadimgi bronza davri madaniyatiga oid yodgorlik bo‘lib, millioddan avvalgi XIII-XI asrlarga oid, deb taxmin qilinadi. Bu madaniyatlar ko‘p asrlar davomida bir-biri bilan hamkorlikda yashaganini va turli etnik guruhlarning madaniy merosini o‘zida mujassam etganini ko‘rsatadi.

Masalan, S.P. Tolstov¹ tomonidan o‘rganilgan Tazabagyab madaniyatlari ham Qoraqalpog‘istonning arxeologik salohiyatining muhim qismi bo‘lib, ularni o‘rganish natijasida bronza davrining ikki madaniyati bir vaqtning o‘zida mavjud bo‘lgani ma‘lum bo‘lgan. Bu esa hududda turli tarixiy etnik va madaniy jarayonlar sodir bo‘lganidan dalolat beradi.

Qoraqalpog‘istonning ushbu yodgorliklari va arxeologik manzillari sayyohlar uchun jozibadorlikni oshirishi mumkin.

Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasining turizm salohiyati juda katta bo‘lib, uni jahon turizm bozoriga zamonaviy marketing vositalari orqali chiqarish imkoni bor. Bu borada ekologik va etnografik turizm muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Ushbu turizm yo‘nalishlari nafaqat hududning iqtisodiy rivojlanishiga, balki uning madaniy merosini saqlash va dunyoga yoyishda ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Mazkur anjuman, ayniqsa, Qoraqalpog‘istonning kelgusi turizm salohiyatini mustahkamlashda, asosiy yo‘nalishlar bo‘yicha ishlab chiqilgan takliflarni keng tatbiq qilishda omil bo‘lib, mahalliy hunarmandchilikni rivojlantirish va yangi turizm xizmatlarini joriy qilishga, hudud aholisi uchun yetarli darajada doimiy va mavsumiy daromadli ish o‘rinlari yaratishga xizmat qiladi.

1 <https://ensiklopediya.uz>

II-SHO'BA

Etnografik turizmni
tashkil etishning
asosiy xususiyatlari

CLIMATE CHANGE: THE MOST IMPORTANT AND PRESSING ISSUE IN THE MODERN WORLD AND SOLUTIONS

Raquel Noboa

CEO of the «Fifty Shades of Green», Ireland

Founder of Fifty Shades Greener From climate anxiety to climate action

Thank you so much for allowing me to be here today to tell you my story

My name is Raquel Noboa, I am the founder of Fifty Shades greener and I am originally from Spain.

My own career up until 2017 was in Hospitality. To be honest I kind of fell into Hospitality by pure chance. I was 17 years old when my dad offered me a one way ticket to wherever I wanted to go and destiny has it that a week later I landed in Shannon, in the west of Ireland. I had no English at the time and so my only option was to clean bedrooms as a housekeeping assistant for my first year in Ireland, which was a shock to my system at the time.

My immediate family are all academics, my mum is a doctor, my dad a psychologist turned politician and my sister is a marine biologist. When my parents asked me what I wanted

to be when I grew up, I literally had no idea, two things I did know, that I wanted to be challenged by my career but that I also wanted to have fun at my job everyday. Needless to say they all thought I was crazy, or lazy, or a little mix of both.

I've never been a person that learned through books or conventional educational methods. Back when I was young, I felt inferior and not good enough because I learnt in a different way than my family members.

I have carried those feelings of inferiority pretty much my entire adult life, I always felt that I had failed on my education. But I was blessed to fall into Hospitality the way I did, all of a sudden I found that place in the world were I could learn by doing, I could learn by watching others doing their job and it led me to have an amazing career with many different managerial positions around the world.

It was 2012 when I started learning

about sustainability. Back then, Climate Change was not spoken about as often as it is now by regular people like me, at the time I thought that carbon emissions and green house gases were things that only scientist and governments argued about.

Unfortunately, I had already experienced firsthand what nature can do to humanity. I was working in the Maldives in 2004 when a Tsunami hit the Indian ocean on the 26th of December, destroying so many lives in just a few minutes.

From that day on I suffered from Eco anxiety for more than a decade, but of course at the time I did not know what it was, which makes you think you are a bit crazy on top of feeling anxious which is not a great combination.

My turning point was when I was working at Hotel Doolin in the West of

Ireland and I learnt how to measure our business carbon emissions. This is when I realized that if I could measure those emissions, I also could manage them and most importantly reduce them. It then became my life's mission to learn more about sustainability and I started creating the 50 step programme for sustainability in Hospitality, so I could teach other people how to measure, manage and reduce their environmental impact.

Knowledge is powerful, most importantly, it is empowering. My eco anxiety started to get better, because I felt there was something I could do about Climate Change, however small that contribution might be. If I reduced my workplace carbon emissions, I was finally doing my best for the planet we all share, and that made me feel powerful within my own life.

In 2017 I finally took the plunge, and I founded Fifty Shades Greener as an environmental education company, and my life mission became to teach others what I had learned on my own Green Journey.

I personally started my green journey by reducing 3 resources, 3 things that every person and every business in the world can manage better, that is the energy and water that we use, and the waste we produce.

I was born in a country where these resources were

readily available to me. I didn't have to make any effort, because I could flick a switch or open a tap and there they were. I also never had to think about waste, I put it in the bin outside and it disappears as if by a magic trick.

In many parts of the world, we have become societies of resource over use, and we have lost the connection between our own individual use of those resources, and the damage their causing on the environment.

Let me show you a practical example of the things I learnt about environmental sustainability within my workplace

I used to do a lot of early shifts in my time as a Hotel Manager, and I realised that our breakfast chef use to arrive every morning at 6am, and turn every single machine in the kitchen on, even those machines that he would not use until later. When I asked him about it, he said that was his routine, what he had done all his life as a chef, he would turn everything on ready for a busy day ahead. And quite honestly, how could you blame him? He had never seen our electricity or energy bills, and nobody had ever told him any different. I also

found out, that our main oven used 38Kwh of electricity and that our electricity unit price was 0.15 cent per hour. So if we were to turn off that oven for just for one extra hour a day, everyday, we would reduce our electricity use by nearly 14,000 kw, reducing 4.8 tonnes of CO2 from our emissions, which would save us over €2000 in one year. This was just one machine, off for an extra hour a day, which may seem like a really small thing to do, generating really big results.

Within 2 years of the start of my green programme at Hotel Doolin we had reduced our energy use by 30%, waste by 40% and water by 25%, only by implementing simple systems and processes to change our teams behaviour around their use of utilities. Imagine what those savings meant to our business bottom line. 5 years later Hotel Doolin became the first carbon neutral hotel in Ireland and established itself as the Hotel of choice for the green traveler market increasing their bookings by 40%

Over the past 6 years I have built a team of 8 people, we have worked with CEOs, governments, businesses,

Qoraqalpog'iston turizm infratuzilmasi
Туристическая инфраструктура Каракалпакстана
Tourism infrastructure of Karakalpakstan

colleges and universities upskilling people in developed countries to become resource efficient. We are also creating qualifications at all levels of education. 3 years ago we started working with secondary school students, who at the age of 15 are now able to measure and reduce their environmental impact and feel empowered to make changes to their own lives. What's most important for me, is that our programmes provide action based learning, to suit students like me, but also because true Sustainable development will not be achieved by rehearsing books or understanding learning outcomes, it will be achieved by society taking action.

I saw this infographic on social media last month and I found it very relevant to the some of the problems we have. It simply explains how the blame game is one of the reason why humanity is not acting fast enough to stop climate change, the public blames corporations for making too much stuff but corporations blame the public for buying all the stuff they make. Corporations and the public blame the government for not creating policies and laws to stop harmful activities and governments blame corporations and the public because change is difficult and everyone wants business as usual.

The key to change this vicious circle is Education.

Education can ensure that our future leaders, business owners and individuals of society have a proper understanding of sustainable development, taking personal responsibility for their own actions without looking around to blame others.

I heard a young climate activist from Australia once say: Climate change is not your responsibility, as it is outside of your control, what is your responsibility are all the things within your control.» And I found this statement to be very powerful because it reminds us all, that we all have the power to do better within our own lives.

Our lives and the things we do everyday, have an effect on the environment in some way. Every time we turn on a light, we are using energy and producing carbon emissions, every time we buy something, anything! that product has carbon emissions associated with it, and it will also become waste at some point.

Our behavior matters, our behavior has an impact on the planet, and we as individuals, are the only people in charge of our own behavior.

I am not an environmental scientist nor a climate change expert, I am simply a person that has seen firsthand what nature can do to humanity, I am a person that believes we are destroying our own home and the lives of billions of people. Sustainability is not about saving the planet, is about saving humankind.

It is up to each of us, to be the solution we want to see.

Qoraqalpog'iston turizm infratuzilmasi
Туристическая инфраструктура Каракалпакстана
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Qoraqalpog'iston turizm infratuzilmasi
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